

Tissue culture

Rice plantlets obtained from a somatic embryogenic cluster from immature panicle culture *in vitro*

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Immature panicles of a haploid rice plant, a diploid rice plant derived from anther culture of Guang-lu-ai 4 and Zhaung Youyi 2/(Zhen-shan 97A/IR24) F_1 , and an interspecific hybrid/*Oryzae sativa* ($2n=24$)/*O. latifolia* ($2n=48$)/ F_1 ($2n=36$) were used to study plantlet formation through somatic embryogenic cell culture of rice. Inoculation was from initiation of the secondary rachis branches to the late stage of spikelet differentiation, when the immature panicle was about 5 to 25 mm long.

Calli were formed from swollen spikelets. Embryoids were formed from calli 50-60 days after inoculation in the medium HE_5 +2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) 2mg/liter + naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) 2 mg/liter + kinetin 3 mg/liter. When embryoids were cultured in the inducing medium or transferred to a subculturing medium, new embryoids were continually formed and embryogenic cell clusters developed (Fig. 1). The embryogenic cluster in the interspecific hybrid F_1 was white and could easily be separated, but individual embryoids were firm. In the developmental stages there were globular-shaped, heart-shaped, scutellum-shaped, and mature embryoids within the embryogenic cluster (Fig. 2). Proliferation of the cluster of the specific hybrid F_1 was very fast in the MS medium + 2,4-D 2 mg/liter or in the HE_5 + 2,4-D 2 mg/liter + NAA 2 mg/liter + kinetin 3 mg/liter subculture medium, but embryoids of other rice varieties failed to proliferate. Embryoids proliferated and germinated quickly (Fig. 3) when they were transferred in the MS + kinetin 2 mg/liter differentiating medium. The average frequency of plantlet differentiation from the embryogenic cluster is 83-

85% and differentiating ability can be maintained more than 10 months. New buds could be seen 2-3 days after transfer

and new embryoids continually occurred as the buds were regenerated and plantlets were formed (Fig. 4). □

1. Embryogenic cluster of the interspecific hybrid F_1 , electromicroscope scanning $\times 40$.

3. A germinating embryoid, electromicroscope scanning $\times 300$.

2. Single embryoids separated from an embryogenic cluster. G : globular embryoid, H : heart-shaped embryoid, S : scutiform embryoid $\times 30$.

4. Plantlets regenerated from an embryogenic cluster.